

Synthesis of a new series of oxadiazoles and triazoles as antimicrobial agents

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Abstract : 2-{4'-(2''-Chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-thione, 3-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-thione and their N and S substituted derivatives have been synthesized and screened for their antimicrobial potential against human pathogenic fungi *Candida albicans* (CA), *Cryptococcus neoformans* (CN), *Aspergillus fumigatus* (AF), *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (TM), *Candida parapsilosis* (ATCC-22019) (CP) and bacteria *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (ATCC-27736) (KP), *Escherichia coli* (ATCC-9637) (EC), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCCBAA-427) (PA) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC-25923) (SA). The structures of the compounds have been established by means of elemental analysis and spectral data (IR, PMR and Mass).

Keywords : 1,3,4-Oxadiazolin-5-thione, 1,2,4-triazolin-5-thione, aminomethylation, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

1,3,4-Oxadiazoles have been reported to possess antibacterial¹, fungicidal², anticancer³, anticonvulsant⁴, anti-inflammatory⁵ and herbicidal⁶ activities. Particularly 2,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been found to exhibit diverse biological activities such as antibacterial⁷, anti-HIV⁸, antitubercular⁹, virucidal¹⁰, antimalarial¹¹, muscle relaxants¹², anti-inflammatory¹³, anthelmintic¹⁴, hypnotic¹⁵ and lipid per oxidation inhibitor¹⁶. Similarly 1,2,4-triazoles have been shown to exhibit antimicrobial¹⁷, anti-inflammatory¹⁸, analgesic¹⁹, antitumor²⁰, antihypertensive²¹, anticonvulsant²², antiviral²³ and plant growth regulatory²⁴ activities. Keeping this biological activity profile of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles and 1,2,4-triazoles and in continuation²⁵ of our work on biologically active heterocycles in the present communication a new series of N and S substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazoles and 1,2,4-triazoles is being reported.

4-(2'-Chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazine²⁶ (2) was prepared by the hydrazinolysis of methyl 4-(2'-chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoate²⁶ (1) which in turn was obtained by the O-benylation of methyl 4-hydroxybenzoate

with 2-chlorobenzyl chloride. 4-(2'-Chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazine (2) was cyclised with carbon disulphide and potassium hydroxide²⁷ followed by acidification to the corresponding 2-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-thione (3). Mannich condensation on 3 with primary and secondary amines in the presence of formaldehyde gave 4-aminomethyl-2-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-thiones (4-17). 1,3,4-Oxadiazolin-5-thione (2) when treated with chlorobenzyl chlorides in alcoholic potassium hydroxide yielded 5-substitutedbenzylthio-2-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (18-22) while on reaction with substituted aroyl chlorides in aqueous sodium hydroxide gave 5-substitutedaroylthio-2-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (23-27) (Scheme 1). 4-(2'-Chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazine (2) on treatment with phenyl isothiocyanate gave 1-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoyl}-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (28) which underwent cyclization in the presence of sodium hydroxide to give 3-{4'-(3''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-thione (29). Triazolin-5-thione (29) on being subjected to aminomethylation with primary and second-

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ary amines in the presence of formaldehyde resulted into 3-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1-aminomethyl-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-thiones (30-43). Compound 29 on reaction with chlorobenzyl chlorides in alcoholic potassium hydroxide and substituted aroyl chlorides in aqueous sodium hydroxide gave 5-substitutedbenzylthio-3-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazoles (44-48) and 5-substitutedaroylthio-3-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazoles (49-53) respectively (Scheme 2).

Antimicrobial activity :

Compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity

against human pathogenic fungi *Candida albicans* (CA), *Cryptococcus neoformans* (CN), *Aspergillus fumigatus* (AF), *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (TM), *Candida parapsilosis* (ATCC-22019) (CP) and bacteria *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (ATCC-27736) (KP), *Escherichia coli* (ATCC-9637) (EC), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCCBAA-427) (PA) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC-25923) (SA) by Macrobroth Two Fold Serial Dilution Technique²⁸. Compounds were tested at 100 µg/mL concentration in DMSO and MIC values were determined in µg/mL. Fluconazole and gentamycin were taken

R_1 = Morpholino, piperidino, pyrrolidino, *N*-methylpiperazino, *N*-ethylpiperazino, *N*-phenylpiperazino, *N*-benzylpiperazino, dimethylamino, diethylamino, anilino, 4-methylanilino, 4-methoxyanilino, 4-chloroanilino, 4-fluoroanilino; R_2 = benzyl, 2-chlorobenzyl, 3-chlorobenzyl, 4-chlorobenzyl, 2,4-dichlorobenzyl; R_3 = benzoyl, 4-nitrobenzoyl, 4-methoxybenzoyl, 4-chlorobenzoyl, cinnamoyl

(a) 2-Chlorobenzyl chloride, K_2CO_3 , DMF; (b) $N_2H_4 \cdot H_2O$, EtOH; (c) CS_2 , KOH, EtOH; (d,i) amines, CH_2O , DMF; (e,j) benzyl chlorides, KOH, EtOH; (f,k) aroyl chlorides, NaOH; (g) PhNCS, EtOH; (h) NaOH

as standard drug for antifungal and antibacterial screening. The antimicrobial activity data are presented in Table 2.

Antifungal activity :

Among the 4-aminomethyl-2-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-thiones (4-17), compounds 4, 5, 7 and 17 were found to be equipotent showing MIC 3.12 $\mu g/mL$ against *Candida albicans*. Compounds 6, 8 and 15 showed MIC 6.25 $\mu g/mL$ against *Candida albicans*

while 9, 10, 12 and 14 showed MIC 12.5 $\mu g/mL$ against *Candida albicans*. In case of Mannich bases with *N*-substituted piperazines, Mannich base with *N*-methylpiperazine (MIC 3.12 $\mu g/mL$) was found to be more effective against *Candida albicans* than Mannich base with *N*-ethylpiperazine (MIC 6.25 $\mu g/mL$) whereas Mannich bases with *N*-phenyl and *N*-benzylpiperazine, both showed MIC 12.5 $\mu g/mL$. Compounds 4, 5, 6 and 15 all showed MIC 6.25 $\mu g/mL$ against *Cryptococcus neoformans*. In case of antifungal activity against *Aspergillus*

Table 1. Characterization data of compounds prepared

Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :			Molecular formula
						Found (Calcd.)			
						C	H	N	
3	-	-	-	240-242	86	56.41 (56.51)	3.32 (3.45)	8.70 (8.79)	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂ S
4	Morpholino	-	-	142-144	80	57.41 (57.48)	4.72 (4.79)	10.00 (10.05)	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O ₃ S
5	Piperidino	-	-	136-138	76	60.61 (60.64)	5.22 (5.29)	10.02 (10.10)	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ ClN ₃ O ₂ S
6	Pyrrolidino	-	-	130-132	85	59.70 (59.77)	4.93 (4.98)	10.41 (10.46)	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O ₂ S
7	<i>N</i> -Methyl- piperazino	-	-	148-150	82	59.49 (58.53)	5.30 (5.34)	12.93 (13.00)	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ClN ₄ O ₂ S
8	<i>N</i> -Ethyl- piperazino	-	-	166-168	78	59.33 (59.39)	5.58 (5.62)	12.54 (12.59)	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ ClN ₄ O ₂ S
9	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- piperazino	-	-	118-120	78	63.31 (63.35)	5.00 (5.07)	11.34 (11.37)	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ ClN ₄ O ₂ S
10	<i>N</i> -Benzyl- piperazino	-	-	142-144	67	63.93 (63.96)	5.27 (5.33)	11.00 (11.05)	C ₂₇ H ₂₇ ClN ₄ O ₂ S
11	Dimethyl- amino	-	-	88-90	69	57.49 (57.52)	4.72 (4.79)	11.11 (11.18)	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O ₂ S
12	Diethyl- amino	-	-	138-140	65	59.39 (59.47)	5.40 (5.54)	10.33 (10.40)	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ ClN ₃ O ₂ S
13	Anilino	-	-	136-138	82	62.25 (62.33)	4.18 (4.25)	9.83 (9.91)	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O ₂ S
14	4-Methyl- anilino	-	-	146-148	83	62.98 (63.08)	4.50 (4.57)	9.50 (9.60)	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O ₂ S
15	4-Methoxy- anilino	-	-	134-136	66	60.76 (60.85)	4.35 (4.41)	9.17 (9.26)	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O ₃ S
16	4-Chloro- anilino	-	-	168-170	76	60.18 (60.26)	4.28 (4.36)	9.10 (9.17)	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S
17	4-Fluoro- anilino	-	-	156-158	67	57.55 (57.64)	3.64 (3.71)	9.10 (9.17)	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ FN ₃ O ₂ S
18	-	Benzyl	-	128-130	62	64.58 (64.62)	4.12 (4.16)	10.20 (10.28)	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₂ S
19	-	2-Chloro- benzyl	-	152-154	68	59.55 (59.59)	3.57 (3.61)	6.29 (6.32)	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
20	-	3-Chloro- benzyl	-	170-172	72	59.54 (59.59)	3.56 (3.61)	6.29 (6.32)	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
21	-	4-Chloro- benzyl	-	128-130	80	59.54 (59.59)	3.56 (3.61)	6.27 (6.32)	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
22	-	2,4-Dichloro- benzyl	-	126-128	79	55.21 (55.28)	3.10 (3.14)	5.75 (5.80)	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ Cl ₃ N ₂ O ₂ S
23	-	-	Benzoyl	156-158	80	62.44 (62.48)	3.49 (3.55)	6.58 (6.62)	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₃ S

Table-1 (contd.)

24	-	-	4-Nitro-benzoyl	186-188	72	56.67 (56.60)	2.93 (2.99)	8.94 (8.98)	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ CIN ₃ O ₅ S
25	-	-	4-Methoxy-benzoyl	172-174	80	60.90 (60.99)	3.71 (3.75)	6.13 (6.18)	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ CIN ₂ O ₄ S
26	-	-	4-Chloro-benzoyl	156-158	69	57.70 (57.76)	2.98 (3.06)	6.08 (6.12)	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S
27	-	-	Cinnamoyl	128-130	70	64.17 (64.21)	3.74 (3.79)	6.19 (6.24)	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ CIN ₂ O ₃ S
28	-	-		180-182	67	61.15 (61.23)	4.30 (4.37)	10.12 (10.20)	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ CIN ₃ O ₂ S
29	-	-		228-230	74	63.97 (64.04)	3.97 (4.06)	10.59 (10.67)	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ CIN ₃ OS
30	Morpholino	-	-	172-174	80	63.29 (63.35)	4.89 (5.07)	11.30 (11.37)	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ CIN ₄ O ₂ S
31	Piperidino	-	-	166-168	72	66.00 (66.05)	5.47 (5.50)	11.39 (11.41)	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ CIN ₄ OS
32	Pyrrolidino	-	-	150-152	68	65.40 (65.43)	5.20 (5.24)	11.72 (11.75)	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ CIN ₄ OS
33	N-Methyl-piperazino	-	-	172-174	70	63.81 (63.84)	5.89 (5.91)	13.75 (13.79)	C ₂₇ H ₃₀ CIN ₅ OS
34	N-Ethyl-piperazino	-	-	166-168	73	64.64 (64.67)	6.09 (6.15)	13.42 (13.47)	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ CIN ₅ OS
35	N-Phenyl-piperazino	-	-	146-148	65	67.64 (67.66)	5.25 (5.28)	12.28 (12.33)	C ₃₂ H ₃₀ CIN ₅ OS
36	N-Benzyl-piperazino	-	-	150-152	60	68.00 (68.09)	5.47 (5.50)	11.95 (12.03)	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ CIN ₅ O ₂ S
37	Dimethyl-amino	-	-	116-118	70	53.25 (53.28)	5.05 (5.10)	12.40 (12.43)	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ CIN ₄ OS
38	Diethyl-amino	-	-	136-138	72	65.17 (65.20)	5.61 (5.64)	11.67 (11.70)	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ CIN ₄ OS
39	Anilino	-	-	120-122	77	67.32 (67.40)	4.54 (4.61)	11.15 (11.23)	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ CIN ₄ OS
40	4-Methyl-anilino	-	-	156-158	76	67.82 (67.90)	4.80 (4.87)	10.83 (10.92)	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ CIN ₄ OS
41	4-Methoxy-anilino	-	-	154-156	70	65.77 (65.84)	4.65 (4.73)	10.50 (10.59)	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ CIN ₄ O ₂ S
42	4-Chloro-anilino	-	-	164-166	72	62.97 (63.03)	4.04 (4.12)	10.42 (10.50)	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ Cl ₂ N ₄ OS
43	4-Fluoro-anilino	-	-	160-162	72	65.10 (65.17)	4.19 (4.26)	10.80 (10.86)	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ ClFN ₄ OS
44	-	Benzyl	-	170-172	72	69.37 (69.49)	4.48 (4.55)	8.61 (8.68)	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ CIN ₃ OS
45	-	2-Chloro-benzyl	-	144-146	72	64.84 (64.86)	3.99 (4.05)	8.06 (8.10)	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ OS
46	-	3-Chloro-benzyl	-	132-134	68	62.84 (64.86)	3.98 (4.05)	8.05 (8.10)	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ OS

Table-1 (contd.)

47	-	4-Chloro- benzyl	-	126-128	72	64.82 (64.86)	4.00 (4.05)	8.08 (8.10)	$C_{28}H_{21}Cl_2N_3OS$
48	-	2,4-Dichloro- benzyl	-	126-128	70	50.78 (60.81)	3.56 (3.61)	7.57 (7.60)	$C_{28}H_{20}Cl_3N_3OS$
49	-	-	Benzoyl	210-212	78	67.50 (67.53)	3.98 (4.02)	8.40 (8.44)	$C_{28}H_{20}ClN_3O_2S$
50	-	-	4-Nitro- benzoyl	128-130	70	61.90 (61.93)	3.47 (3.50)	10.27 (10.32)	$C_{28}H_{19}ClN_4O_4S$
51	-	-	4-Methoxy- benzoyl	174-176	70	65.92 (65.97)	4.14 (4.17)	7.93 (7.96)	$C_{29}H_{22}ClN_3O_3S$
52	-	-	4-Chloro- benzoyl	186-188	81	63.12 (63.15)	3.50 (3.57)	7.86 (7.89)	$C_{28}H_{19}Cl_2N_3O_2S$
53	-	-	Cinnamoyl	166-168	86	68.73 (68.76)	4.17 (4.20)	7.99 (8.02)	$C_{30}H_{22}ClN_3O_2S$

Table 2. Minimum inhibitory concentration MIC ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) of compounds against pathogenic fungi and bacteria by macrobroth two fold serial dilution technique

Compd	CA	CN	AF	TM	CP	KP	EC	PA	SA
3	50	50	50	25	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100
4	3.12	6.25	3.12	3.12	12.5	25	>100	12.5	>100
5	3.12	6.25	3.12	3.12	>100	25	12.5	>100	>100
6	6.25	6.25	12.5	3.12	25	25	25	50	>100
7	3.12	25	6.25	3.12	25	12.5	>100	50	>100
8	6.25	>100	6.25	3.12	6.25	3.12	>100	50	>100
9	12.5	>100	6.25	6.25	>100	>100	>100	50	>100
10	12.5	>100	6.25	6.25	>100	>100	>100	50	>100
11	25	>100	>100	12.5	50	>100	>100	>100	>100
12	12.5	>100	>100	12.5	50	>100	>100	>100	>100
13	50	>100	>100	12.5	50	>100	>100	>100	>100
14	12.5	>100	12.5	12.5	50	50	50	50	50
15	6.25	6.25	12.5	6.25	>100	25	>100	50	>100
16	50	>100	50	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100
17	3.12	>100	50	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	50
18	>100	>100	50	25	>100	>100	>100	>100	50
19	3.12	>100	50	6.25	50	50	>100	50	>100
20	>100	>100	50	25	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100
21	3.12	>100	>100	6.25	25	>100	>100	>100	>100
22	50	>100	50	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100
23	>100	50	6.25	6.25	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100
24	12.5	50	6.25	6.25	>100	>100	>100	50	>100
25	12.5	50	6.25	6.25	>100	>100	>100	50	>100
26	>100	50	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100
27	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100
28	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
29	50	50	50	50	>100	>100	>100	>100	12.5
30	6.25	12.5	6.25	12.5	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100

Table-2 (contd)

31	6.25	12.5	6.25	12.5	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
32	6.25	25	6.25	6.25	6.25	6.25	> 100	> 100	> 100
33	6.25	25	6.25	> 100	> 100	50	> 100	> 100	> 100
34	6.25	25	3.12	> 100	> 100	50	> 100	> 100	> 100
35	> 100	25	6.25	> 100	> 100	50	> 100	> 100	> 100
36	> 100	25	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
37	> 100	25	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	50
38	> 100	25	25	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	50
39	> 100	50	50	> 100	> 100	50	> 100	> 100	50
40	12.5	50	25	50	> 100	50	> 100	> 100	50
41	12.5	50	25	50	> 100	25	> 100	> 100	50
42	25	25	25	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
43	25	12.5	25	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
44	> 100	50	25	50	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
45	> 100	50	25	50	> 100	25	> 100	> 100	> 100
46	> 100	50	25	50	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
47	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	6.25	6.25	> 100	> 100
48	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	6.25	6.25	> 100	> 100
49	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	50	> 100	> 100	> 100
50	> 100	3.12	3.12	> 100	> 100	50	> 100	> 100	> 100
51	> 100	6.25	6.25	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
52	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
53	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100

Compound 28 was not screened for its antifungal and antibacterial potential.

lus fumigatus, compounds 4 and 5 both were found to be equipotent showing MIC 3.12 µg/mL. Similarly compounds 7, 8, 9, 10 and 14, 15 showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL and 12.5 µg/mL respectively against *Aspergillus fumigatus*. Compounds 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 showed MIC 3.12 µg/mL against *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* while 9, 10 and 15 showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL whereas 11, 12, 13 and 14 showed 12.5 µg/mL. Compound 4 showed MIC 12.5 µg/mL and 8 showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL against *Candida parapsilosis*. Out of five, 5-substitutedbenzylthio-2-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (18-22), compounds 19 and 21 showed MIC 3.12 µg/mL against *Candida albicans* and MIC 6.25 µg/mL against *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*. Among the 5-substitutedaroylthio-2-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (23-27), compounds 24 and 25 showed MIC 12.5 µg/mL against *Candida albicans* and 6.25 µg/mL against *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* respectively.

Among the Mannich bases (30-43) of triazoles, triazoles

(30-34) with morpholinomethyl, piperidinomethyl, pyrrolidinomethyl, *N*-methyl and *N*-ethylpiperazinomethyl groups showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL against *Candida albicans* while compounds 40 and 41 having 4-methylanilinomethyl and 4-methoxyanilinomethyl substituent showed MIC 12.5 µg/mL against *Candida albicans*. Compounds 30, 31 and 43 showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL against *Cryptococcus neoformans* while 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38 and 42 showed equipotency with MIC 25 µg/mL against *Cryptococcus neoformans*. Compounds 30, 31, 32, 33 and 35 showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL against *Aspergillus fumigatus* whereas 34 showed 3.12 µg/mL. Compounds 38, 40, 41, 42 and 43 showed MIC 25 µg/mL against *Aspergillus fumigatus*. Compounds 30 and 31 showed MIC 12.5 µg/mL against *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* while 32 showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL. Compound 32 showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL against *Candida parapsilosis*. From the antifungal activity data of oxadiazoles and triazoles, Mannich bases of oxadiazole were found to be more active than

that of triazole, may be because of bulky structure of triazole. In both the cases it was found that Mannich bases were more active than that of parent oxadiazole and triazole. Among the 5-substitutedbenzylthio-3-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazoles (**44-48**) and 5-substitutedaroylthio-3-{4'-(3''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazoles (**49-53**). Compounds **44**, **45** and **46** showed MIC 25 µg/mL against *Aspergillus fumigatus*. Compound **50** was found to be effective against *Cryptococcus neoformans* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* showing MIC 3.12 µg/mL while **51** showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL against *Cryptococcus neoformans* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*. From the detailed study of antifungal data it was found that none of the compounds showed antifungal activity comparable to that of fluconazole and the data showed so much diversity that no clear cut structure activity relationship could be established.

Antibacterial activity :

Among the Mannich bases of oxadiazoles (**4-17**), compound **7** and **8** showed MIC 12.5 and 3.12 µg/mL against *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Compound **5** showed MIC 12.5 µg/mL against *Escherichia coli*. Compound **4** was found to show MIC 12.5 µg/mL against PA just half of the standard drug, gentamycin, whereas compounds **5**, **6**, **7**, **8**, **9**, **10**, **14** and **15** showed MIC 50 µg/mL, double to the standard drug against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Out of *S*-benzyl (**18-22**) and *S*-aroyloxadiazoles (**23-27**), only **19**, **24** and **25** showed MIC 50 µg/mL against PA again double to standard drug. From the Mannich bases of triazolin-5-thione (**30-43**), only one compound **32** with pyrrolidinomethyl group showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* while **33**, **34** and **35** were found to show MIC 50 µg/mL, double to that of gentamycin. Out of 5-substituted-benzylthio-3-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazoles (**44-48**) and 5-substitutedaroylthio-3-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazoles (**49-50**), only two compounds **47** and **48** with 4-chlorobenzyl and 2,4-dichlorobenzyl substituents showed MIC 6.25 µg/mL against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Escherichia coli* respectively. Rests of the triazoles were found to be either inactive or showing MIC of no value.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes in

sulfuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer IR spectrophotometer. PMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX-300 instrument using CDCl₃ as solvent. TMS was taken as internal reference. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ ppm. Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol-JMS-300 spectro-meter at 70 eV. Purity of compounds was checked by TLC silica gel G plates and spots were located by iodine vapors. The physical data of the compounds prepared are presented in Table 1.

2-{4'-(2''-Chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-thione (**3**) :

A mixture of 4-(2'-chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazine (**2**) (0.01 mol), potassium hydroxide (0.015 mol) and carbon disulphide (0.015 mol) in ethanol (95%, 75 mL) was refluxed for 8 h. Excess of solvent was distilled off and remaining material was poured into ice cold water and acidified with acetic acid. The compound thus obtained was filtered and dried; IR (cm⁻¹) : 3470 (NH), 1255 (CH₂O), 1167 (C-O-C), 1070 (C=S), 750 (C-Cl); MS (*m/z*) : 318 (M⁺), 320 (M+2).

4-Morpholinomethyl-2-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-thione (**4**) :

To a suspension of compound **3** (0.005 mol) in DMF, formaldehyde (37% aq. solution, 0.5 mL) and morpholine (0.005 mol) were added with vigorous stirring. The solution was warmed for 2 min on a water bath and then left at room temperature overnight. Solid compound thus obtained was filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallised from chloroform-pet. ether (60-80 °C) (1 : 1).

Compounds **5-17** were prepared by similar method using different primary and secondary amines.

(**4**) : IR (cm⁻¹) : 2955 (>N-CH₂-N<), 1248 (-CH₂O-), 1170 (C-O-C), 1072 (C=S), 748 (C-Cl); PMR (CDCl₃) : 2.83-2.86 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 3.67-3.73 (4H, t, -CH₂-O-CH₂-), 4.56 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.08-7.90 (8H, m, Ar-H); MS (*m/z*) : 417 (M⁺), 419 (M+2); (**5**) : PMR (CDCl₃) : 1.60-1.74 (6H, m, -CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-), 2.82-2.86 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 4.56 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.93-7.90 (8H, m, Ar-H); (**6**) : PMR (CDCl₃) : 1.57-1.64 (4H, m, -CH₂-CH₂-), 2.82-2.87 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 4.53 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.83-7.60 (8H, m, Ar-H); MS (*m/z*) : 401 (M⁺), 403 (M+2);

(7) : IR (cm^{-1}) : 2945 ($>\text{N-CH}_2\text{-N}<$), 1258 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 1172 (C-O-C), 1072 (C=S), 748 (C-Cl); PMR (CDCl_3) : 2.50 (3H, s, N-Me), 2.63-2.76 (4H, t, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-N-CH}_2-$), 3.13-3.23 (4H, t, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-N(Me)-CH}_2-$), 4.56 (2H, s, $>\text{N-CH}_2\text{-N}<$), 5.25 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 6.98-7.80 (8H, m, Ar-H); MS (m/z): 430 (M^+), 432 ($\text{M}+2$); (8) : PMR (CDCl_3) : 1.04-1.07 (3H, t, CH_3), 2.26-2.31 (2H, q, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.43-2.51 (4H, t, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-N-CH}_2-$), 2.64-2.93 (4H, t, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-N(Et)-CH}_2-$), 4.61 (2H, s, $>\text{N-CH}_2\text{-N}<$), 5.25 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 7.04-8.28 (8H, m, Ar-H); (9) : PMR (CDCl_3) : 2.40-2.59 (4H, t, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-N-CH}_2-$), 2.67-2.89 (4H, t, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-N(Ph)-CH}_2-$), 4.60 (2H, s, $>\text{N-CH}_2\text{-N}<$), 5.25 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 6.91-7.78 (13H, m, Ar-H); (10) : PMR (CDCl_3) : 2.40-2.59 (4H, t, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-N-CH}_2-$), 2.77-3.01 (4H, t, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-N(CH}_2\text{Ph)-CH}_2-$), 3.49 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 4.60 (2H, s, $>\text{N-CH}_2\text{-N}<$), 5.25 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 6.91-7.78 (13H, m, Ar-H); (11) : PMR (CDCl_3) : 3.10 (6H, s, $-\text{N(Me)}_2$), 4.55 (2H, s, $>\text{N-CH}_2\text{-N}<$), 5.25 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 6.89-7.70 (8H, m, Ar-H); (13) : IR (cm^{-1}) : 3232 (NH), 2936 ($>\text{N-CH}_2\text{-N}<$), 1258 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 1170 (C-O-C), 1072 (C=S), 748 (C-Cl); PMR (CDCl_3) : 3.37 (1H, s, NH), 4.64 (2H, s, $>\text{N-CH}_2\text{-N}<$), 5.25 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 7.69-8.70 (13H, m, Ar-H); (14) : PMR (CDCl_3) : 2.23 (3H, s, Me), 3.35 (1H, s, NH), 4.70 (2H, s, $>\text{N-CH}_2\text{-N}<$), 5.25 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 6.88-7.93 (12H, m, Ar-H); MS (m/z) : 437 (M^+), 439 ($\text{M}+2$); (15) : PMR (CDCl_3) : 3.45 (3H, s, OMe), 3.35 (1H, s, NH), 4.68 (2H, s, $>\text{N-CH}_2\text{-N}<$), 5.25 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 6.87-7.63 (12H, m, Ar-H).

5-Benzylthio-2-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazole (18) :

A mixture of compound 3 (0.005 mol) and benzyl chloride (0.005 mol) in alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (5%, 20 mL) was refluxed for 8 h. It was cooled and poured into ice cold water. The solid mass thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from CHCl_3 : MeOH (5 : 1).

Compounds 19-22 were prepared in a similar manner using variously chlorosubstituted benzyl chlorides.

(18) : IR (cm^{-1}) : 2806 ($-\text{SCH}_2-$), 1510 (C=N), 1253 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 1171 (C-O-C), 750 (C-Cl); PMR (CDCl_3) : 4.38 (2H, s, $-\text{SCH}_2-$), 5.25 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 7.10-7.99 (13H, m, Ar-H); MS (m/z) : 408 (M^+), 410 ($\text{M}+2$); (22) : IR (cm^{-1}) : 2836 ($-\text{SCH}_2-$), 1507 (C=N), 1255

($-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 1171 (C-O-C), 749 (C-Cl); PMR (CDCl_3) : 4.45 (2H, s, $-\text{SCH}_2-$), 5.25 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 7.08-8.03 (11H, m, Ar-H).

5-Benzoylthio-2-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazole (23) :

Compound 3 (0.005 mol) was dissolved in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 50 mL) and benzoyl chloride (0.005 mol) was added to it dropwise and whole contents were stirred for 1 h. The precipitate thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from CHCl_3 : MeOH (5 : 1).

Compounds 24-27 were prepared opting same procedure and different substituted aryl chlorides.

(23) : IR (cm^{-1}) : 1688 (thioester), 1255 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 1171 (C-O-C), 750 (C-Cl); PMR (CDCl_3) : 5.25 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 7.50-8.29 (13H, m, Ar-H); MS (m/z) : 422 (M^+), 424 ($\text{M}+2$); (25) : IR (cm^{-1}) : 1677 (thioester), 1255 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 1171 (C-O-C), 748 (C-Cl); PMR (CDCl_3) : 3.78 (3H, s, OMe), 5.25 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 7.48-8.19 (13H, m, Ar-H); (26) : IR (cm^{-1}) : 1680 (thioester), 1255 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 1172 (C-O-C), 748 (C-Cl); PMR (CDCl_3) : 5.25 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 7.38-8.29 (13H, m, Ar-H).

1-{4'-(2''-Chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoyl}-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (28) :

4-(2'-Chlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazine (2) (0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (50 mL) and to it phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) was added and refluxed for 3 h. Solid compound thus separated on cooling was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

3-{4'-(2''-Chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-thione (29) :

Compound 28 was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (5%, 50 mL) and refluxed for 3 h, cooled to room temperature and neutralized with dilute hydrochloric acid. White crystalline compound thus obtained was filtered, washed several times with water and dried; IR (cm^{-1}) : 3430 (NH), 1250 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{O-}$), 1080 (C=S), 756 (C-Cl); MS (m/z) : 393 (M^+), 395 ($\text{M}+2$).

3-{4'-(2''-Chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1-morpholino-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-thione (30) :

Formaldehyde (37% aq. solution, 0.5 mL) and morpholine (0.005 mol) were added to a suspension of 3-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-phenyl-1,2,4-

triazolin-5-thione (**29**) (0.005 mol) in DMF with vigorous stirring. The reaction mixture was warmed on a water bath for 2 min and left overnight at room temperature. The solid product thus separated was filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallised from chloroform-pet. ether (60–80 °C).

Compounds **31–43** were synthesized adopting same procedure with different primary and secondary amines.

(**30**) : IR (cm⁻¹) : 2945 (>N-CH₂-N<), 1257 (-CH₂O-), 1082 (C=S), 758 (C-Cl); PMR (CDCl₃) : 2.93–2.96 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 3.71–3.76 (4H, t, -CH₂-O-CH₂-), 4.74 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.28–7.90 (13H, m, Ar-H); MS (*m/z*) : 492 (M⁺), 494 (M+2); (**31**) : IR (cm⁻¹) : 2948 (>N-CH₂-N<), 1257 (-CH₂O-), 1072 (C=S), 755 (C-Cl); PMR (CDCl₃) : 1.58–1.65 (6H, m, -CH₂CH₂CH₂-), 2.83–2.89 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 4.64 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.89–7.60 (13H, m, Ar-H); MS (*m/z*) : 490 (M⁺), 492 (M+2); (**32**) : PMR (CDCl₃) : 1.60–1.67 (4H, m, -CH₂CH₂-), 2.80–2.84 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 4.51 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.89–7.60 (13H, t, Ar-H); (**33**) : PMR (CDCl₃) : 2.01 (3H, s, N-Me), 2.33–2.39 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 4.64 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.81–7.62 (13H, m, Ar-H); (**36**) : PMR (CDCl₃) : 2.39–2.47 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 2.52–2.62 (4H, t, -CH₂-N(CH₂Ph)-CH₂-), 3.34 (2H, s, -CH₂Ph-), 4.61 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.81–7.90 (18H, m, Ar-H); (**40**) : PMR (CDCl₃) : 2.23 (3H, s, Me), 3.36 (1H, s, NH), 4.68 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.80–7.80 (17H, m, Ar-H); (**41**) : PMR (CDCl₃) : 3.43 (3H, s, OMe), 3.37 (1H, s, NH), 4.65 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.87–7.80 (17H, m, Ar-H); (**43**) : IR (cm⁻¹) : 3376 (NH), 2939 (>N-CH₂-N<), 1255 (-CH₂O-), 1074 (C=S), 1030 (C-F), 754 (C-Cl).

5-Benzylthio-3-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole (**44**) :

A mixture of 3-{4'-(2''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-thione (**29**) (0.005 mol) and benzyl chloride (0.005 mol) in alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (5%, 50 mL) was refluxed for 4–5 h. It was diluted with ice cold water and filtered. Solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from CHCl₃ : MeOH (5 : 1).

Compounds **45–48** were prepared similarly using different chlorobenzyl chlorides.

(**44**) : IR (cm⁻¹) : 2816 (-SCH₂-), 1253 (-CH₂O-), 750 (C-Cl); PMR (CDCl₃) : 4.35 (2H, s, -SCH₂-), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.09–8.09 (18H, m, Ar-H); MS (*m/z*) : 483 (M⁺), 485 (M+2); (**46**) : IR (cm⁻¹) : 2828 (-SCH₂-), 1255 (-CH₂O-), 748 (C-Cl); PMR (CDCl₃) : 4.30 (2H, s, -SCH₂-), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.30–8.19 (17H, m, Ar-H).

5-Benzoylthio-3-{4'-(3''-chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole (**49**) :

3-{4'-(2''-Chlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazolin-5-thione (**29**) (0.005 mol) was dissolved in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 60 mL) and benzoyl chloride (0.005 mol) was added dropwise with stirring, the reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h. After completion of the reaction, the precipitated compound was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from CHCl₃ : MeOH (5 : 1).

Compounds **50–53** were prepared similarly using different substituted aryl chlorides.

(**49**) : IR (cm⁻¹) : 1680 (thioester), 1255 (-CH₂O-), 750 (C-Cl); PMR (CDCl₃) : 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.55–8.19 (18H, m, Ar-H); MS (*m/z*) : 497 (M⁺), 499 (M+2); (**51**) : IR (cm⁻¹) : 1671 (thioester), 1255 (-CH₂O-), 748 (C-Cl); PMR (CDCl₃) : 3.83 (3H, s, OMe), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.38–7.99 (17H, m, Ar-H); (**52**) : IR (cm⁻¹) : 1680 (thioester), 1255 (-CH₂O-), 748 (C-Cl); PMR (CDCl₃) : 3.83 (3H, s, OMe), 5.25 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.32–7.99 (17H, m, Ar-H); (**53**) : IR (cm⁻¹) : 3063 (-CH=CH-), 1700 (thioester), 1255 (-CH₂O-), 748 (C-Cl).

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